

An Overview of Job Embeddedness: A Review Study

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Abstract:- This study presents an overview of job embeddedness including the dimensions, the related concepts of job satisfaction. The purpose of the study is to learn about the various reviews. Further, the study explores the different authors that are affecting the job embeddedness of employees from different IT sector based on earlier studies. The study uses existing literature review to learn about the job embeddedness and job satisfaction. This study focuses on several reviews. The findings of the study reveal that the job embeddedness is most important influencing. Job embeddedness may be used to develop the job satisfaction strategies following on-the-job and off-the-job. So basically, this study is based on several review.

Keywords:- Job Embeddedness, Employee.

I. JOB EMBEDDEDNESS

According to Mitchell et al., (2001) introduced a new conceptual framework known as job embeddedness. It is derived from the Lewin's field theory, the term of job embeddedness represents a wide asterism of influences (Mitchell et al., 2001) on an employee's intent to stay and can be considered as a net or a web in which one can become stuck (Mitchell et al., 2001). It is represented a unique factor in understanding why people stay at their current jobs and discussed ways in which employers can be influence employees' embeddedness and inclination to stay. They recommended are mainly three components such as links, fit, and sacrifice—each in an organizational i.e., on-the-job and community i.e., off-the-job.

➤ *Table 1 Visualizes the Six Components of Job Embeddedness.*

Table 1 Job Embeddedness Dimensions

	Links	Fit	Sacrifice
Organization	Links organization	Fit organization	Sacrifice organization
Community	Links community	Fit community	Sacrifice community

➤ Links

According to Mitchell et al., (2001) links are defined as the observable connections between employee's and organization. The high links to the organization, the more highly embedded employee's will become. It can be psychological, social and include age, marital status etc.,

church-related activities, and membership in community organizations.

- *Organization:*

Organization- links are formal or informal connections that exist between an employee and other people or groups in the organization. It mainly includes relationships with co-workers, members of work groups, and others. So that these work relationships can be influence personal embeddedness and intention to quit both positively and negatively.

- *Community:*

Links-community: it is recognizing the significant influence of friends and other social institutions and also their influence on decision making. It can be just as important to retention as organizational links. It is that activities include relationships, and environmental factors can be influencing an individual's intent to stay.

- *Fit*

According to Mitchell et al., (2001) it can be defined as employee's perceived compatibility or comfort with an organization and environment. The fit between an employee and their environment or community is an important components of job embeddedness.

- *Organization:*

The term of fit-organization dimensions is examining how well an employee views themselves as sharing compatible goals, characteristics and values with the potential employer and other employees within the any organization. The better the fit, the greater the possibility the employee will be stay.

- *Community:*

According to Mitchell, et al., (2001) it is referred a fit-community concept to address the nonwork factors that can help rising workers' intention to stay at their current jobs. It is also capturing how well a people perceives he/she fits into their surrounding community and environment.

- *Sacrifice*

It is the last and final dimension of the job embeddedness construct. It is referring to the psychological and material benefits that an individual would lose at any given time if he/she choose to quit the any organization. According to Shaw et al., (1998) the greater the sacrifice, the more difficult the decision to quit will be. As with the

dimensions of links and fit, sacrifice also has organization and community dimensions.

- **Organization:**

Organizational sacrifices can take various forms. It may be possible for an employee to locate a current job with a similar salary and benefits etc. However, there are many few indubitable organizational sacrifices that may be employees should consider. There may be new retirement and benefit restrictions or some other benefits.

- **Community:**

Community sacrifices usually are an issue only if relocation is required with a new job. In many cases, an individual's loss of community can represent too great a sacrifice. The main sacrifice between the employee and the community is a much highly important attribute of job embeddedness for an employee who must relocate to change the current jobs.

- **Job Satisfaction**

According to Khalib et al. (2015) referred the term of job satisfaction as the extent to which an employee like or dislike their current jobs in any organization. According to Umamaheswari and Krishnan (2015) suggested an employee satisfaction could contribute to enhanced organizational commitment, reduced intent to leave, and ultimately enhanced retention rates. the importance of job satisfaction, managers should work toward raising employee satisfaction to help improve efficiency, production, employee retention and working effectively. This human resource concept of job satisfaction remains most important to any organizations.

II. PRIOR RESEARCH ON JOB EMBEDDEDNESS

- **Tian A. W., et al., (2016)**

Stated that Ability-enhancing HRM, Motivation-enhancing HRM, Opportunity-enhancing HRM, Organisational fit, Organisational sacrifice, Organisational links, Task performance. Matched sample was opted to collect the data. And valid responses of 197 Chinese state-owned firm employees and their supervisors were collected. Data analysed were with the help of multiple mediation test, Confirmatory factor analysis and recorded on Seven-point Likert scale for further analysis. The results revealed that HRM practices were contribute to the creation and development of embeddedness, and also the improvement of job performance. The results suggested that organisations can be proactively enhanced both embeddedness and employee performance through implementing appropriate HRM practices.

- **Ghosh S.K., (2017)**

Stated that the relationship between job insecurity and unethical pro-organizational behaviour were moderated by job embeddedness. the results showed that the role of job insecurity and job embeddedness as important factors influencing unethical pro-organizational behaviour. It was analysed that revealed that both job insecurity and job

embeddedness were positively linked to unethical pro-organizational behaviour. 346 responses were collected from employees of different Indian organizations and the data were analysed with the multiple regression technique.

- **Linder, C., (2019)**

Stated that in this study data were collected from two groups: managers of assigned expatriate workers and self-initiated expatriate workers and recorded on Five-point Likert scale the data were analyzed with the help of a partial least squares (PLS) analysis. And also used the surveys assessed workers' motivations for going abroad, and differences between the two groups were compared by analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results confirmed with the positive relationships between the degree of organisational embeddedness in institutions abroad and job performance and career satisfaction. Additionally, the perceptions of embeddedness were depended on workers' mindsets regarding their career ambitions.

- **Alikhani B. A., (2016)**

This study reviewed the result offered a founded that there are differences in structural terms as well as in the composition of the networks. In this study delivered were founded on the differences of social network embeddedness between organizationally embedded and self-initiated employees and also introduces SNA to the field of global mobility research. The methodologically a mixed-methods were conducted with the help of qualitative interviews and social network analysis (SNA) to investigated the structure of the respondent's social support ego networks.

- **Singh R., (2018)**

Examined that supported for the propositions that organizational embeddedness was predicts workplace deviance and that employee work engagement moderates the organizational embeddedness– workplace deviance relationship. The Confirmation was another significant, positive relationship between organizational embeddedness and workplace deviance. Furthermore, confirmed that significant moderating effect of employee work engagement in the organizational embeddedness– workplace deviance relationship. A study was conducted frontline employees across the financial services sector in the Caribbean nation of Trinidad. 465 valid responses were collected and measured on Five points Likert scale. Data were analysed with the help of a three-step multiple hierarchical regression analysis and convenience sampling approach were used.

- **Treuren G.J.M., and Halvorsen B., (2016),**

Indicated that high levels of PCB weaken the relationship between client embeddedness and job satisfaction. In additional, for employers, the client embeddedness was affected likely to improved employee retention, job satisfaction, affective commitment and employee engagement in this study. Two-wave survey was conducted 121 true responses were stored of employees working and measured on five-point Likert scale. For data analysis, Regression and ANOVA was used.

➤ *Marasi, S., et al., (2016)*

Revealed that Online survey was opted to collect the data. 353 valid responses were considered for the study and the data were analyzed with the help of hierarchical regression. It was found that job embeddedness was signified moderated the organizational trust-workplace deviance relationship. Also, significant the participants who experienced low organizational trust and high job embeddedness were engaged in more workplace deviance than those experiencing low organizational trust and low job embeddedness were found.

➤ *Maden C., (2014)*

Depicted that apart from perceived recognition, all the perceived high-involvement HR practices were positively related to employees' work engagement, which in turn predicted their learning goal orientation. Furthermore, the findings of this study revealed that the employees' perceptions of (i.e., empowerment, competency development, information sharing and fair reward practices) are positively related to work engagement. Valid responses from 240 actual users were accumulated. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the help of AMOS software package confirmed the research model and measured on five-point Likert-type scale.

III. CONCLUSION

By means of an elaborate review of literature, one thing comes to know that the assessment of employee job satisfaction is a complex phenomenon as it involves several factors that are to be reckoned with. In this study, job satisfaction also varies in accordance with different gender age groups, educational levels, levels of management, marital status, work experience, etc. The job embeddedness structure has been presented as a better conceptualization of the employee-employer relationship because the job embeddedness focuses on retention instead of turnover. The job embeddedness is built on various research findings and has increased the understanding of assorted areas of employer-employee interaction. All conspicuous components of job embeddedness are grounded in distinctly expressed, well-respected, and also sometimes such as classic literature. So that it is important to realize that most important interventions should ideally use the marvelous potency of both the organization i.e., on-the-job embeddedness, and the community i.e., off-the-job embeddedness. So that this is basically a review-based study paper.

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